

Camera-Pose Robust Crater Detection from Chang’e 5

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As space missions aim to explore increasingly hazardous terrain, crater-based pose estimation (CBPE) may provide the accurate and timely position estimates required to ensure safe navigation. Crater-detection algorithms (CDAs) are a crucial initial step to CBPE, using images collected from a spacecraft’s onboard cameras to detect impact craters in the environment. Existing literature has proposed many algorithms for crater detection, however performance has only been evaluated within a narrow operating scenario. In this work, we demonstrate the challenge in detecting craters from images containing off-nadir view angles, using Mask R-CNN, a state of the art detection algorithm. We demonstrate training on real-lunar images is superior to a simulated dataset despite lacking training images containing off-nadir view angles, achieving detection performance of 63.1% F_1 -score and ellipse-regression performance of 0.701 intersection over union. This work provides the first quantitative analysis of CDA performance on images containing off-nadir view angles. Towards the development of robust CDAs, we additionally provide the first annotated dataset with off-nadir view angles from the Chang’e 5 Landing Camera, available here: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11326449>.

1 Introduction

Accurate pose estimation of spacecraft is increasingly valuable as future missions aim to explore hazardous yet scientifically valuable terrain, such as the upcoming Artemis III mission to the lunar South Pole. Recent investigations into vision-based navigation systems have utilized camera measurements cross-referenced with onboard maps to provide accurate estimations of pose [1, 2]. A crucial initial step for vision-based navigation is detection of salient features from camera measurements [1]. For planetary bodies without thick atmospheres (eg. the Moon and asteroids), impact craters provide a valuable source of detectable and persistent landmarks visible on the surface [3]. Techniques to detect such impact craters from imagery are named crater-detection algorithms (CDAs),

with a pipeline shown in Fig. 1.

Existing literature explores CDA performance in a narrow operating scenario, often using a digital-elevation map (DEM) or strictly nadir-pointing images as input. In this work, we provide the first analysis of detection performance on real optical imagery with off-nadir view angles, through a newly annotated dataset from the Chang’e 5 Landing Camera.

Figure 1: Steps of CDA pipeline, demonstrating bounding box detection and ellipse regression on image from the Chang’e 5 landing camera [4].

2 Related Works

There exists significant literature describing the creation and evaluation of CDAs under similar operating conditions [5–8]. Typically, these algorithms aim to increase the completeness of crater catalogues on planetary bodies such as the Moon or Mars by automating detection of new craters [9–11]. As such, a DEMs is often used as input, as this data is free from variation due to lighting or view angle [5]. However, for optical

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navigation, crater detection from a DEM is constraining as these maps require many measurements to be accurately defined [12]. For crater-based pose estimation (CBPE), it is preferable to detect craters from optical imagery, as this would be readily available during a spacecraft’s flight.

CDAs using real optical imagery are relatively less explored. Yang et al. applied 7 notable CDAs to an optical imagery dataset collected from the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) Narrow-Angle Camera (NAC), demonstrating state-of-the-art detection performance of 86.97% F_1 -score with a Faster R-CNN architecture [13]. Mao et al. applied a Dual U-Net architecture to optical imagery collected from the LRO Wide-Angle Camera, in addition to a DEM, demonstrating that this additional data source leads to with improved performance as compared to 4 CDAs using only the DEM [14]. While these CDAs predict from optical imagery, again their relevance to CBPE is questionable as images are strictly nadir-pointing [15]. During orbit and landing, a spacecraft may view the surface at off-nadir view angles which could decrease detection performance and consequently reduce the accuracy of pose estimation.

The only analysis of CDA performance with off-nadir view angles is provided by Maas et al. using a novel segmentation-based CDA on both simulated images of the near-earth asteroid Eros in 2016 and real images from Chang’e 3 in 2020 [2, 3]. While both datasets contain significant off-nadir view angles, a quantitative analysis of CDA performance was not performed.

2.1 Contributions

In this work, we describe the annotation of the first CDA dataset with significant off-nadir view angles, using images collected from the Chang’e 5 Landing Camera [4]. Addressing off-nadir view angles constitutes a significant advancement to existing analyses as these view angles can obscure already complex surface morphology [16]. We analyze the performance of Mask R-CNN (M_{RCNN}), a state of the art CDA from literature, after training on real and simulated datasets [11, 17]. We demonstrate that, despite a lack of training samples with off-nadir view angles, datasets containing real lunar images achieve best detection and ellipse-regression performance.

3 Datasets

Three crater-detection datasets are used in this work, each containing images of the lunar surface supervising with the visible impact craters. A brief summary

of each dataset is included in Table 1, with four supervised samples from each shown in Fig. 2.

3.1 CE5-CDA

CE5-CDA is a newly annotated crater-detection dataset supervising images collected by the Chang’e 5 Landing Camera [4]. This dataset contains 132 images, hand-labelled by expert annotators. Craters present within each image are described with a bounding ellipse of the crater rim. The first 100 images of the lander’s descent were labelled to create a training set, and every tenth image of the remaining 313 were labelled to create the testing set. A temporal split was performed to reduce data leakage between the training and testing set while emulating a realistic operating scenario where human annotators label a period of historic data and require the CDA achieve similar performance into the future.

CE5-CDA, like many crater-detection datasets, provides an incomplete annotation of visible craters. In the initial stages of the lander’s descent, its high altitude allowed the landing camera to capture large regions of the lunar surface, often containing >300 visible craters per image. For practical reasons these images could not be labelled exhaustively, so annotators were instructed to prioritise large craters with a well-defined rim. These craters were prioritized as they are more visually distinct from the rest of the surface and assumed to be more reliably detected by a CDA. On average, the dataset contains 50 labelled craters per image, with later images within the dataset containing fewer annotations, as fewer craters were visible as the lander approached the surface.

To our knowledge, CE5-CDA is the first annotated CDA dataset of real-lunar images containing off-nadir view angles, and the first annotated dataset of the Chang’e 5 landing camera. Hence, as part of this work, we make the CE5-CDA dataset available to the research community for further analysis.

3.2 CRESENT

CRESENT is a dataset of rendered images of the lunar surface, generated using a DEM [18, 19]. Images were rendered from 100km above the surface, with off-nadir view angles ranging between 0 to 60 degrees, in increments of 10 degrees, mimicking the expected orbital conditions of a lunar surveillance mission [18].

This simulated dataset is valuable as camera pose is known exactly for each image, allowing automated supervision of images by projecting Robbin’s crater catalogue onto the surface [20].

Notably, as no complete lunar-crater catalogue exists, annotation of craters present within each image is

Dataset	Image Source	Images	View angles	Labels	Label Format
CE5-CDA	Chang'e 5 Landing Camera	132	0 – 60° off-nadir*	6535	Bounding Ellipse
CRESENT	Rendered using DEM	2694	0 – 60° off-nadir	142102	Bounding Ellipse
LRO-NAC	LRO Narrow Angle Camera	20	0° off-nadir	23250	Bounding Circle

Table 1: Summary of CDA datasets. * View angles for CE5-CDA are estimates as camera pose is unknown.

Figure 2: Four samples from each CDA dataset, with annotated craters shown by a green-bounding ellipse.

incomplete. As such, many CRESENT images contain multiple unlabelled instances of craters that appear obvious to the human-eye, as shown in the bottom-left sample of CRESENT images in Fig. 2. The subset of CRESENT images within 0-75E, 0-30N was used for practical purposes. A 20% random stratified split of images from each off-nadir view angle was selected as a validation set.

In comparison to datasets of real lunar images, the lunar surface visible in CRESENT’s images is well lit noticeably smoother. This is likely a result of the resolution of the DEM used to render each image.

3.3 LRO-NAC

LRO-NAC is a manually supervised dataset of 20 images from the LRO NAC, containing over 20 000 annotated craters [13]. While the LRO-NAC contains the fewest images of all datasets utilized in this work, it is a valuable source of real lunar images and contains a wide range of lighting conditions. Similarly to CE5-CDA and CRESENT, LRO-NAC has incomplete annotation, however it provides the most complete annotation of visible craters of the three datasets, with hundreds of annotations per image. The relative completeness of this dataset as compared to CE5-CDA and CRESENT is clearly visibly in Fig. 2. However, the quality of individual crater annotations within this

dataset is poor in comparison to CE5-CDA and CRESENT, with many annotations being noticeably larger than the crater rim. In addition to this, bounding circles rather than bounding ellipses were annotated.

4 Methodology

In this section, we describe the training and evaluation process of M_{RCNN} . M_{RCNN} is a specialization of Faster R-CNN, a two-stage object detection architecture that has exhibited high performance across a large range of computer vision tasks, including state-of-the-art performance in crater detection [13, 21]. M_{RCNN} uses a specialized head to predict a segmentation mask, a binary mask with the same resolution as the input image, where masked pixels represent the presence of an object in the original image. After training, the near-elliptical segmentation mask produced by M_{RCNN} is fit with an ellipse using a least-square fitting algorithm[22, 23].

4.1 Training

Training was performed with a stochastic gradient descent optimizer until validation loss plateaued, at which point the best performing weights were restored. Where two datasets were used, training and validation was performed on the first dataset until

performance plateaued, these weights were then used to initialize training on the second dataset. The two datasets were not joined to allow CDAs to update spurious learned relationships once training on the initial dataset had concluded.

Training was performed on a g4dn.16xlarge AWS instance, with GPU acceleration using a Tesla T4. Training time varied depending on the dataset, taking < 3 hours to train on CRESENT, < 40 minutes on LROC-NAC and < 15 minutes on CE5-CDA.

4.2 Evaluation

CDA performance was evaluated for detection and ellipse-regression separately. Detection performance was evaluated using F_1 -score, where true positive (T_p) predictions are determined by the intersection-over-union (IoU) of predicted and ground-truth bounding boxes being greater than 0.5. Ellipse-regression performance of each T_p is then evaluated, by projecting ellipses at the same resolution of the input sample. The intersection and union were then calculated at pixel resolution on the projected ellipses to calculate the Ellipse IoU (E_{IoU}).

5 Results

Detection and ellipse-regression performance of M_{RCNN} was evaluated after training on different combinations of the datasets described in Sec. 3. Best detection and ellipse-regression performance was achieved by first training on LRO-NAC, then CE5-CDA, as shown in Table 2. This suggests that initially training on real-lunar images with nearly complete annotation was advantageous, despite containing LRO-NAC only 12 training images and strictly nadir-pointing view angles.

Training Dataset(s)	F_1 -score	E_{IoU}	$E(T_p)$
CRESENT	6.9%	0.557	1.3
LRO-NAC	16.6%	0.549	8.0
CE5-CDA	60.0%	0.687	18.7
CRESENT + CE5-CDA	54.3%	0.674	18.3
LRO-NAC + CE5-CDA	63.1%	0.701	22.2

Table 2: CDA performance on CE5-CDA test set. The expected number of T_p predictions is included as many pose estimation algorithms require a minimum of 5 to function [1, 3].

Although CRESENT provides training samples with off-nadir view angles, more training images and

Figure 3: Reduction in detection and ellipse-regression performance over frame number of finetuned CDAs. The end of the training-set and beginning of the test-set is denoted with a grey-dotted line.

more crater instances to learn from, initially training on this dataset reduced overall detection performance. Training on CE5-CDA alone outperformed CRESENT + CE5-CDA, suggesting there were spurious learned relationships from the simulated dataset that reduced performance. CDA performance without training on CE5-CDA was also evaluated, yielding poor results. This suggests that existing datasets are not sufficient for generalizing to real images containing off-nadir view angles.

Fig. 4 shows ellipse-regressions from each of the 5 CDAs evaluated. Many false positive predictions visible in these samples (shown in red) appear to be real-unlabelled instances, demonstrating the impact of incompleteness in annotation. While the incompleteness of CE5-CDA is a limitation of the dataset, it is representative of the incompleteness of real-lunar crater catalogues. In operation, a CDA may produce detections of visible craters that are not catalogued, which may be considered false positives as they are useless of pose estimation.

As the Chang’e 5 lander approached the surface, the landing camera recorded images from both decreasing altitudes and off-nadir view angles [4]. Fig. 3 shows the CDA pretrained on LRO-NAC demonstrated the best generalization from the training set to this new scenario, in both detection and ellipse-regression.

6 Discussion

In Sec. 5, we demonstrate that simulated images are currently insufficient for pretraining a CDA, perhaps due to the quality of simulated images used in this work. Future work may explore improving the quality of rendered images by augmenting existing DEMs to simulate a more detailed surface. Additionally, the heterogeneity of the simulated dataset could be easily

Figure 4: Sample images from CE5-CDA, with crater detections. Each row shows a single sample from the CE5-CDA test set, while columns separate detections from each CDA. Blue ellipses denote ground truth, while green and red ellipses show true positive and false positive predictions respectively.

improved by rendering images under a wider range of lighting conditions and different regions of the lunar surface. Should these high-quality simulated images improve CDA performance, large heterogeneous training sets could be generated at little cost, likely further improving crater detection performance. Future work may explore how domain adaptation could bridge the simulated-to-real domain gap to improve performance where few real lunar images are available.

Future work may additionally explore automated labelling of real lunar images by projecting known crater catalogues onto existing mosaics using position metadata. As demonstrated in this work, real lunar images are necessary for best CDA performance, however manual labelling of large datasets is infeasible. Automated annotation of lunar mosaics could leverage the large volume of publicly available data from the National Aeronautics Space Administration (NASA) or Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) to curate a large dataset at little cost. This could allow manual labelling efforts to be focused towards annotating the Chang’e 3, 4 and 6 mission data, which contain off-nadir view angles but do not contain position metadata.

Future work may also investigate the effect of lighting conditions in tandem with camera-pose on CDA performance. Such analysis could inform whether strategic collection of images in a power-constrained environment may result in best crater-detection performance, and consequently higher quality pose estimations.

7 Conclusion

In this work, we provide the first quantitative analysis of CDA performance on real lunar images containing off-nadir view angles. We demonstrate that an existing state-of-the-art CDA achieves poor performance in this operating scenario, but can be improved through an additional set of training data. While training on simulated images containing off-nadir view angles yielded no improvement, training on real nadir-pointing lunar mosaics improved both detection and ellipse-regression performance, achieving 63.1% F_1 -score $0.701E_{IoU}$ respectively. For development of robust CDAs, we show that the inclusion of off-nadir training images is necessary for sufficient detection performance in this operating scenario.

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